

CHALLENGES OF MEASURING CONVERSION RATE IN CONDITIONS OF AI GENERATED PRODUCT SEARCH

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Abstract: *Electronic commerce has changed drastically since the pandemic, and now by the use of artificial intelligence (AI) is changing significantly. There are many ways in which artificial intelligence is changing e-commerce, and in this paper, the focus is on product search. More efficient product search, thanks to artificial intelligence, enables an increase in conversion rates, as one of the indicators that e-retailers track the most. Although conversion rates are relatively low, they tend to grow, and with artificial intelligence, e-commerce finally brings the right product, to the right customer, at the right time and under the required conditions, bringing an efficiency component to each of these parameters.*

Keywords: *e-commerce, conversion rate, artificial intelligence, Amazon, product.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Most customers today expect sellers and manufacturers to understand their unique needs, and artificial intelligence (AI) is becoming the basis for differentiating from the competition. Oosthuizen, et al. (2020) discuss in their research how traditional business models, especially in retailing, are facing disruption by new entrants (driven by technology) who can deliver greater value to customers more efficiently. Artificial intelligence facilitates the product search, finds optimal solutions in relation to customer needs. New opportunities and challenges are opening up in electronic commerce. As a result, the following critical questions arise:

- Do customers use AI-generated search to discover e-commerce products?
- Are users finding the right products thanks to AI search?
- If users reach an e-retailer thanks to AI-generated search results, will they convert, ie. make a purchase?, and finally
- How to get an electronic store listed in AI generated search results?

In the digital era, AI-personalized recommendation has been deeply applied in electronic commerce, it has a remarkable promoting effect on consumers' purchasing behavior and effectively increases the sales volume of e-commerce platforms (Ying, Qiu & Wang, 2025). Saleh & Zeebaree (2025) concluded that driven by AI big data analytics, optimize customer journeys and drive personalized marketing campaigns, addressing data privacy and scalability issues in the process to bring about substantive business growth. Furthermore, Yin, Qiu & Wang (2025) research emphasizes that if information quality improves, the positive impact of technology acceptance on clicking intention will be enhanced showed; it shows consumers' experiences of AI-personalized recommendations and clarifies how these experiences affect the clicking intention and offers valuable insights for e-commerce platforms to continuously optimize personalized recommendation algorithms and boost the click conversion rate of online shopping. In Kuman and Trakru (2020) research emphasize that the application of AI and machine learning enhances the sale of Amazon drastically.

The premise of the work is that if potential customers receive more efficient and accurate search results thanks to artificial intelligence (AI), then it is more likely that they will buy the product they found thanks to the search with AI, that is, that the AI-generated search increases the conversion rate, because those who really want to buy products come to the electronic store, the precision of the search in accordance with the customer's requirements is higher. Therefore, the display and information about products on the electronic store should be adapted to AI searches.

2. MEASUREMENT AND MEANING OF CONVERSION RATE IN ELECTRONIC COMMERCE

In e-commerce, the average conversion rate is a percentage that measures how effective an electronic store is at persuading users to take a desired action. It can be downloading content, signing up for an e-mail list or most importantly buying a product. The conversion rate is measured by simply dividing the number of purchases by the visits made during a certain period, and then multiplying by 100:

$$\text{Conversion rate} = (\text{Number of purchases} / \text{Total number of visitors}) \times 100 \quad (1)$$

For example, if an electronic store has 5000 visitors per month and has 50 sales, the conversion rate would be:

$$(50 / 5000 \text{ visitors}) \times 100 = 1\% \text{ conversion rate}$$

So, if the electronic store has 1,000 visits and 100 products purchased in a certain period, the conversion rate is $100/1,000 = 0.10$, or 10%. Which of these two percentages will be satisfactory depends on the set goals of the electronic retailer, that is, the activities undertaken in the previous period.

More customers are interested in online shopping after COVID, so the average conversion rate after the pandemic has increased, habits have changed, and many customers are realizing the real advantage of online shopping. Historical evolution of e-commerce conversion rates show changes in average conversion rate by year (SpeedCommerce, 2025):

- 2000-2010: Static interfaces and limited trust led to conversion rate of 1.5%-2.5%.
- 2010-2020: Improved UX/UI and payment options boosted conversion rate to 2.5%-4.0%.
- 2020-2024: Pandemic-driven spikes stabilized at 3.0%-4.2% post-COVID.
- 2025: Ongoing growth in personalization and mobile optimization maintains conversion rate at 2%-4%.

The height of the conversion rate largely depends on the type of e-commerce, products, visitors and many other factors. Based on the above percentages, the average conversion rate of e-commerce can be calculated, which is between 2-4%. This means that 2 to 4 out of every 100 visitors make a purchase on electronic stores. That may sound like a small percentage, but conversion rates are actually on an upward trend. The average conversion rates for the six most common product categories in e-commerce are (Adobe for Business, 2025):

- Fashion and apparel: 2.7%
- Health and beauty: 3.3%
- Entertainment: 2.5%
- Household goods: 2.1%
- Electronics: 1.9%
- Food and beverage: 4.6%

What do these percentages show? Why does perhaps the most searched product category on the web, fashion and apparel, have a low conversion rate? Precisely because of the fact that potential customers do a lot of searching, find the most suitable offers and often end up making a purchase in the offline sales store. On the other hand, a product category that is not popular for shopping on the web, such as food and beverages, has a high conversion rate, due to the fact that those who actually intend to buy that way, complete the purchase process after searching. From the above, we can conclude that the potential more effective application of AI in web search can be precisely in these product categories that have lower conversion rates.

3. CHALLENGES AND ADVANTAGES OF AI GENERATED PRODUCT SEARCH

Internet searches are undergoing a fundamental change. Search Engine Optimization (SEO) has been a key component of digital marketing in e-commerce. However, the optimization of online stores according to search engine SEO requirements and the general behavior of customers when searching for information online are likely to experience major changes in the future. Understanding the factors that drive AI-powered search behavior can inform the design of more effective AI systems and marketing strategies (Pham, et al., 2024).

The emergence of generative AI (GenAI) search tools such as Chatbot, ChatGPT and DeepSeek are emerging as new channels for finding products and services online. Chatbot will welcome a user to

conversation, guide to customer to make purchase which will reduce customer's struggle, ask customers all the relevant questions to find the perfect fit, style, and color for them (Shafi, et al, 2020). For online customers, this functionality has enabled searches with more complex and specific requirements compared to traditional searches based on keywords and paid ads.

For the effective use of AI-generated product searches, which should result in an increase in the conversion rate, it is first of all necessary to identify and monitor AI-based searches on the electronic store: the number of AI search over time (weekly/monthly), which page of the electronic store they come to (home page, product listing page, product detail page, etc.), how many visitors arrived on the e-store for the first time, conversion flow, i.e. what percentage of search AI ends up buying, what products, etc.

AI-powered search still accounts for fewer conversions, but it is growing rapidly and will tend to grow as its benefits, efficiency and effect on conversion rates are realized. As AI search tools become more ubiquitous, electronic stores need to proactively ensure their content is visible. How much this technology is developed is shown from the speed of technology adoption. Namely, it took only 5 days for ChatGPT to reach a million users (Threads 1 hour, Instagram 2.5 months, Spotify 5 months, Facebook 10 months, Twitter 2 years, Netflix 3.5 years) (Buchholz, 2023).

With such strong growth of AI-based solutions, it is not difficult to predict that it could soon represent a significant percentage of the "organic search" of traditional search engines, such as Google. The growth is supported by the fact that it offers truly new and revolutionary ways to interact with the vast amount of information available on the web. ChatGPT offer online customers a great way to quickly find specific products on the web. In the same way, as e-commerce businesses are getting huge benefits by using AI technology, customers also get better experience and satisfaction by using AI-driven e-commerce portals in the form of intelligent visual search, advanced voice search, better aftersales services, etc. (Srivastava, 2021). A purchase made in this way is more likely to be considered a desired purchase rather than an impulse purchase, because the customer will have the intention of finding a specific electronic store and a specific product.

What should be done in order electronic store to be listed in the results of the GenAI Search platform? What this means for the content and structure of the electronic store? As AI-generated search tools become a growing source of online discovery, optimizing electronic commerce pages for AI-driven search is essential. While traditional SEO principles still apply, adapting to the way AI platforms process and retrieve information will be key to maintaining visibility and relevance.

Using a comprehensive labeling scheme for each product is essential, with details such as name, price, availability, description, brand, and especially aggregate ratings and reviews. AI searches depend on this structured data for accurate answers. For example, if a user asks a question about the price of a product, an AI search must answer with certainty if it sees structured pricing data. Unlike keyword-focused SEO, GenAI tools prioritize content that provides context and detail. Greater likelihood is ensured when product descriptions are rich, informative and written in natural language to match the way AI models process information.

One way to improve searches is to present the content of customer reviews on the page, highlighting the best reviews that talk about the use of the product. AI models integrate data from reviews when forming responses. If review text is available, the chance of AI extracting positive product attributes from real users increases. Many product pages now include an FAQ section, which is a good source of data for AI. Efficient solutions are providing clear question and answer pairs that AI can directly grab for search or chat answers, adding a small FAQ below each product with 3-5 common questions about the item (compatibility, materials, warranty, etc.) and concise answers. This structured Q&A content makes AI search result effective when a user asks a similar question.

Understanding what prompts an AI search to connect to an electronic store is valuable information to better understand how customers discover an electronic store and product and what their purchase intention is. The time for hesitation about artificial intelligence is over.

4. APPLICATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN ELECTRONIC COMMERCE AND INFLUENCE ON THE CONVERSION RATE

Artificial intelligence (AI) is driving more innovation in electronic commerce, turning what was a controversial concept until recently into a competitive advantage. AI is no longer just an efficiency tool, AI is revolutionizing the way retailers personalize shopping experiences, optimize product discovery and drive customer engagement. Product search generated by artificial intelligence enables the right product to be connected with the right customers at the right time and under the most appropriate purchase conditions (product price, delivery type, delivery price, delivery time etc.), all in accordance with customer requirements. Artificial intelligence (AI) in electronic commerce can enhance online shopping by using advanced algorithms and machine learning to optimize customer experience and business operations.

The application of AI and machine learning enhances the sale of Amazon drastically, among most famous AI product Alexa is on the top, which helps to collect the training data sets for the algorithms are essential to Amazon's targeted marketing strategy; recommendation system of Amazon uses AI to reveal the product in demand based on customer searches and enhance the total sales by 35% (Kumar & Trakru, 2020). As search behavior evolves, electronic commerce brands that proactively adapt their SEO strategies for AI-driven search will gain a competitive advantage by tracking AI search, engaging AI-referred visitors, and optimizing content for AI-driven indexing.

AI enables electronic commerce platforms to analyze large data sets, enabling personalized product recommendations and trend predictions tailored to individual customers, provide 24/7 customer support, improve response time and satisfaction, predict demand, ensure optimal inventory levels, adjust prices in real time based on market trends, monitor competitor activity and customer behavior, detect fraudulent transactions, and store customer data.

Using artificial intelligence in electronic commerce can simplify operations, reduce costs and deliver highly personalized shopping experiences, driving growth and customer loyalty. As artificial intelligence technology develops, its role in electronic commerce will become even more important, offering innovative solutions to meet the demands of a fast-paced digital market. Retailers not yet adopting AI solutions need to start testing AI or risk being left behind.

As more brands turn to AI to help with product search, Amazon is looking beyond its platform to improve the customer experience. This move increases the chances for customers to find exactly what they need through familiarity with Amazon's store. Once customers are redirected to the brand's website, the brand handles all payments and orders. However, some brands can use the Amazon Prime feature, which allows customers to get the benefits of Prime shipping on their order, even if it's not sold by Amazon.

Previous updates to Amazon's search experience include visual and generative artificial intelligence. The company redesigned its customer support Chatbot and reported that customer satisfaction scores improved with a generative AI upgrade. The largest online retailer has added visual search features to its platform so customers can get faster and more accurate results.

Amazon products have an average conversion rate of 10% to 15%, Amazon Prime members have an even higher percentage, over 74% (Amazon Inc., 2024). That's because many shoppers browsing Amazon are already planning to buy something — if not right away, then soon. Another reason why so many e-retailers use Amazon as one of their platforms to sell their products. But probably the most important reason to track conversion rate is that it's one of the variables that propels ads to the top of search results. To rank ads, Amazon's algorithm takes into account conversion rates and speed of sales. As a result, if an ad has a low conversion rate, the product is less likely to appear on the first page of Amazon search results. Of course, these averages vary significantly by specialization, as with any measurement. Customers want to search and compare products before making a final purchase decision, so more expensive products often have lower conversion rates.

It's hard to say what constitutes a satisfactory conversion rate on Amazon because it varies depending on what it offers. For example, if the conversion rate is 50%, it will be satisfactory. But the situation would be different if you look at the data of this conversion in detail. Suppose there are four sessions and two orders. It is not satisfactory unless the product is sold at a very high price with a large profit margin. Let's assume a conversion rate of just 3%, based on 3,000 sessions and 90 product conversions. It is satisfactory, because it has a large number of sessions and sales.

5. CONCLUSION

The average conversion rate is a percentage that measures how effective an electronic store is at persuading users to take a desired action. The average conversion rate after the pandemic tends to increase, because habits have changed, and many customers see the real advantage of online shopping. A potential more effective application of AI in web search could be product categories that have lower conversion rates. For the effective use of AI-generated product searches that should result in an increase in conversion rates, it is necessary first of all to identify and monitor AI-based searches on the electronic store. Understanding what prompts an AI search to connect to an electronic store is valuable information to better understand how users discover an electronic store and product and what their purchase intentions are. As search behavior evolves, e-commerce brands that proactively adapt their search SEO strategies to be AI-driven will gain a competitive advantage. Previous updates to Amazon's search experience include visual and generative artificial intelligence. The largest online retailer has added visual search features to its platform so customers can get faster and more accurate results. The average conversion rate of e-commerce is between 2-4%, while Amazon products have an average conversion rate of 10% to 15%.

LITERATURE

- Adobe for Business (2025). *Average ecommerce conversion rate benchmarks*. <https://business.adobe.com/blog/basics/ecommerce-conversion-rate-benchmarks>
- Amazon, Inc. (2024). *Amazon Annual Report*. <https://ir.aboutamazon.com/annual-reports-proxies-and-shareholder-letters/default.aspx>
- Buchholz, K. (Jul 7, 2023). *Threads Shoots Past One Million User Mark at Lightning Speed One Million Users*. <https://www.statista.com/chart/29174/time-to-one-million-users/>, datum jun 2025.
- Kumar, T., & Trakru, M. (2020). The colossal impact of artificial intelligence. E-commerce: statistics and facts. *International Research Journal Engineering Technologies (IRJET)*, 6, 570-572.
- Oosthuizen, K., Botha, E., Robertson, J., & Montecchi, M. (2020). Artificial intelligence in retail: The AI-enabled value chain. *Australasian Marketing Journal*, 29(3), 264-273. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ausmj.2020.07.007>
- Pham, V. K., Pham Thi, T. D., & Duong, N. T. (2024). A Study on Information Search Behavior Using AI-Powered Engines: Evidence From Chatbots on Online Shopping Platforms. *SAGE Open*, 14(4). <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440241300007>
- Saleh, R. A., & Zeebaree, S. R. M. (2025). Artificial Intelligence in E-commerce and Digital Marketing: A Systematic Review of Opportunities, Challenges, and Ethical Implications. *Asian Journal of Research in Computer Science*, 18(3), 395–410. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajrcos/2025/v18i3601>
- Shafi, P.M., Jawalkar, G.S., Kadam, M.A., Ambawale, R.R., Bankar, S.V. (2020). AI—Assisted Chatbot for E-Commerce to Address Selection of Products from Multiple Products. In: Dey, N., Mahalle, P., Shafi, P., Kimabahune, V., Hassanien, A. (eds) *Internet of Things, Smart Computing and Technology: A Roadmap Ahead. Studies in Systems, Decision and Control*, 266, Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-39047-1_3
- SpeedCommerce (2025). *2025 eCommerce Benchmarks: Average Conversion Rates By Industry & By Year*. <https://www.speedcommerce.com/insights/ecommerce-benchmarks-conversion-rates-by-industry-over-by-year/>
- Srivastava, A. (2021). The application & impact of artificial intelligence (AI) on E-commerce. *Contemporary issues in commerce and management*, 1(1), 165-75.
- Yin J, Qiu X, Wang Y. (2025). The Impact of AI-Personalized Recommendations on Clicking Intentions: Evidence from Chinese E-Commerce. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Electronic Commerce Research*. 20(1): 21. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jtaer20010021>